

Integrative Brain Imaging: Multi-Modal Fusion for Enhanced Analysis

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ABSTRACT: Medical image fusion techniques are increasingly important in various clinical applications, as they combine information from different types of medical images. In this study, a method for medical image fusion is proposed which makes use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs). Our approach utilizes convolutional network to create a weight map that combines pixel activity information from two input images. Fusion is performed at multiple scales using image pyramids to better match human visual perception. Additionally, we employ a local similarity-based strategy to adaptively adjust fusion modes for decomposed coefficients. Experimental results show that our method produces promising outcomes in terms of both visual quality and objective assessment.

Keywords: Image fusion, Multimodal medical image, Convolutional neural network (CNN), Image Decomposition, Laplacian pyramid, Gaussian pyramid, Weight maps

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of rapid sensor and computer technology advancement, medical imaging has evolved into an indispensable cornerstone across diverse clinical applications, spanning diagnosis, treatment planning and surgical navigation. In order to furnish medical practitioners with comprehensive insights crucial for clinical decision-making, the acquisition of medical images through various modalities such as, Computed Tomography (CT), X-ray, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) and positron emission tomography (PET) have become standard practice. Each modality, owing to its distinct imaging mechanism, offers unique perspectives on organ and tissue information. For example, CT scans are renowned for their accuracy in localizing dense structures like bones and implants, MRI excels in providing intricate soft-tissue details coupled with high-resolution anatomical information, while PET and SPECT imaging offer invaluable functional insights into blood flow and metabolic activity albeit with lower spatial resolution. Acknowledging the complementary nature of information captured by these modalities, multi-modal medical image fusion emerges as a pivotal strategy aimed at amalgamating disparate data sources to generate composite images. These composite images, synthesized through advanced algorithms and incorporating the strengths of each modality, facilitate enhanced visualization and interpretation for medical practitioners. By providing a comprehensive depiction of both anatomical structures and functional processes, multi-modal medical image fusion empowers physicians to make informed and efficient decisions across various clinical scenarios, thereby optimizing patient care and outcomes.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The researches in fusion of medical modalities have opted several mechanisms for developing new algorithms and new models for extracting the features by using these newly created algorithms and models. Majority of the papers are making use of the CNN model for extracting the weight maps from image modalities and later the extracted weight maps will be passed through the layers of CNN for more precision and accurate fusion of the source medical images. Reading through the papers, it is observed that there are some many algorithms based on which the newer techniques and newer models are being built upon. Some papers also perform quality improvements on already existing methods and algorithms. Some of the papers are reviewed here.

A. Medical Image Fusion using Transform Techniques

The paper[1] presents an innovative approach to medical image fusion by implementing edge and energy fusion rules on the decomposed bands of Discrete Wavelet Transformation (DWT) and Stationary Wavelet Transformation (SWT). Specifically, the authors fused MRI and PET scan images, selecting sub-bands based on edges and energy functions. To assess the quality of the composite image, they utilized the entropy method. The results indicate a major improvement in the accuracy of the composite image, by a factor of 0.05. Interestingly, the analysis suggests that Stationary Wavelet Transformation (SWT) outperforms Discrete Wavelet Transformation (DWT) in this context, demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed fusion approach.

B. Multimodal Medical Image Fusion using NSCT and DWT Fusion Framework

The proposed fusion method in this paper[2] combines the Nonsubsampled Contourlet Transform (NSCT) and Discrete Wavelet Transformation (DWT) to enhance the fusion process of medical images. Initially, the input images are decomposed using the NSCT algorithm, and the resulting images are then merged using an energy-based fusion rule. Subsequently, the original input images are decomposed again using the DWT algorithm, and the decomposed images are merged using the same fusion rule as before. The resulting two fused images are further fused using the Edge Strength and Orientation Preservation (ESOP) rule. This multiple steps proposed approach is aiming to enhance the diagnostic quality of composite image based on edges and mutual information for all different medical image modalities. The proposed method demonstrates improved efficiency compared to previous research. However, it is noted that the time taken to generate the final composite fused image is longer compared to other fusion processes. Despite this drawback, the overall enhancement in quality and performance suggests the potential of this method for various medical imaging applications.

C. Multimodal Medical Image Fusion based on Gray Wolf Optimization and Hilbert Transform

This paper[3] presents a novel approach to fuse MRI and PET image modalities using the Gray Wolf Optimization (GWO) algorithm and the Hilbert Transform. The PET image modality is first transformed from RGB to IHS color space to separate intensity and color information. The 2-D Hilbert Transform is applied to the intensity band of both images, and the GWO algorithm is used to fuse them. The composite image is further improved by combining the Intensity (I) band and Hue/Saturation bands using an Inverse Hilbert Transformation. Experimental results show that the GWO algorithm achieves better fusion quality, spectral resolution and spatial resolution compared to other methods, demonstrating its potential for enhancing medical imaging applications.

D. Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine MRI and PET image fusion using the nonparametric density model and the theory of variable-weight

The paper[4] proposes a method for fusing MRI and PET scans to provide more comprehensive and accurate medical imaging. It starts by converting the source images into the IHS color space to separate intensity and color information. The images are then decomposed into detailed layers and base layer coefficients using NSCT. A nonparametric density model is used to combine base layer components, while a maximum fusion strategy based on variable weight theory is used for detail layer components. The independently fused base and detail layers are then combined using inverse NSCT transformation, followed by inverse GIHS transformation to generate the final fused image. This technique preserves color details from PET images and maintains good spatial resolution, making it a promising approach for medical imaging applications.

E. Multi-modality medical image fusion based on image decomposition framework and nonsubsampling shearlet transform

The paper[5] proposes an image fusion algorithm that utilizes guided image filters to address the low contrast issue prevalent in prior research. It decomposes the source image modalities into detailed layer images and base layer images at multiple levels using guided image filters. The algorithm then extracts prominent features from these layers using the Spectral Residual algorithm and a Visual Saliency model based on graphs. Additionally, an established Intensity-Hue-Saturation (IHS) method is employed to combine the base layer and detail layer elements along with their individual eminent features. Fusion of MRI-SPECT/PET image modalities using this method demonstrates improved contrast, albeit with lower color contrast compared to previous approaches.

III. THE PROPOSED METHOD

A. Image Acquisition

The initial phase of medical image fusion entails the acquisition of images from diverse modalities. Each modality offers distinct insights into the internal structures or physiological processes of the body, thus complementing one another in comprehensive diagnostic assessments and treatment planning. For this project, the image modalities are sourced from The Whole Brain Atlas within the Harvard Medical School Database, maintained by Keith A. Johnson, M.D., and his team. This invaluable resource comprises approximately 1000 images spanning various modalities, each corresponding to individual subjects. The rich diversity of modalities and the ample dataset size provided by The Whole Brain Atlas offer an ideal foundation for exploring and developing advanced fusion techniques. By leveraging this extensive dataset, we can effectively train and validate the proposed convolutional neural network (CNN)-based fusion method. The abundance of images covering a wide spectrum of modalities enhances the generalizability and robustness of the developed fusion technique, ensuring its applicability across different clinical scenarios and medical imaging setups.

Fig 1. Dataset

B. Image Preprocessing

Once the images are acquired, preprocessing steps are applied to ensure uniformity and compatible with the process. This may involve correcting for artifacts, aligning the images spatially, and standardizing intensity values to create a common scale across modalities. Preprocessing aims to reduce inconsistencies and improve the accuracy of the fusion process. This process can be used to address issues which are variations in intensity, resolution and noise. The intensities of each individual modalities are adjusted so that intensities of the images are comparable, making the fusion process more effective. Noise reduction techniques such as box filtering, guided filtering are applied to improve the signal-to-noise ratio and enhance the visual quality of the images. Contrast enhancement methods like histogram equalization is used to enhance the visibility of structures and details in the images making them more compatible for fusion. For the fusion of colour images like SPECT, we enhance our fusion approach by incorporating the YUV colour space. This involves initially converting the colour source image from the original RGB space to the YUV space. Subsequently, the Y component is combined with another grayscale image. The ultimate fused image is then generated by converting the intermediate fusion result back from YUV to RGB, while retaining the original U and V components.

Fig 2. The architecture of the Convolutional neural network for training.

C. The CNN model for medical image fusion

The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is applied on the both the image modalities. Convolution involves the application of filters to the input data to detect patterns and features. These filters slide or convolve across the input image to obtain feature maps. The use of pooling layers is to decrease the spatial dimensions of the input images. In our case, max pooling is used where the highest value in a region is preserved. The output from these layers is flattened into a vector. This flattening operation transforms the spatial information into a one-dimensional

representation suitable for input to the fully connected layers. One or more fully bridged layers are used to make predictions based on the features obtained by the convolutional neural network layers. The feature maps from two branches are combined and subsequently fed through two fully connected layers. During training, the network automatically adjusts its weights and biases by minimizing a loss function.

D. Image Decomposition

The schematic diagram of the proposed medical image fusion algorithm is shown in Fig. 3. The algorithm can be summarized as the following steps weight map generation, Pyramid decomposition, and Coefficient fusion.

Fig 3. Schematic diagram of the proposed medical image fusion algorithm

The Laplacian pyramid decomposition is a multiple scale image decomposition technique used in image processing. The process begins by applying a Gaussian blur to the original image to create a smoothed version. After smoothing, the image is down sampled, which results to the first level of the Gaussian pyramid. This process is repeated iteratively to create multiple levels of the pyramid. The Laplacian pyramid is constructed by repeating this process for each level of the Gaussian pyramid. The highest level of the Laplacian pyramid corresponds to the smallest scale, capturing fine details, and the lowest level corresponds to the original image.

The gaussian pyramid decomposition is also used the images after passing through the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). A Gaussian blur is applied on the image to decrease high-frequency details. The image is down sampled , resulting in the first level of the Gaussian pyramid. This process is repeated iteratively on the down sampled images to create multiple levels of the pyramid. Consequently, each coefficient in the network's output map represents the emphasis on a pair of source image patches at a specific location. By assigning this value as the weights for all pixels within the corresponding patch location and subsequently averaging the overlapping pixels, a focus map is created which us maintaining the size of the source images. The ultimate fused image is derived from this focus map which uses the weighted-average rule also making use of the two consistency verification techniques.

E. Fusion Algorithm

The fusion algorithm combines the extracted features from different modalities to create a single composite image. In our case, we are using the Laplacian pyramid reconstruction. The reconstruction involves combining the Laplacian pyramids at different levels to reconstruct the original image. The Laplacian images at each level are up sampled to match the size of the next higher level. This is usually done through interpolation methods, such as bilinear or bicubic interpolation. The reconstruction is performed iteratively from the highest level to the lowest level of the Laplacian pyramid. The reconstruction process effectively combines these scales to reconstruct the original image with the details preserved as in the input modality.

IV. RESULTS

This proposed method merges the combination of CT-MRI and PET-MRI medical images. By integrating data from multiple modalities, it enhances diagnostic accuracy and provides a comprehensive view of anatomical, functional, and molecular information, facilitating improved patient care and advancing medical research.

Fig 4. Results

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed method for medical image fusion using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) represents a significant advancement in the field of multimodal medical imaging. By leveraging CNNs and innovative fusion techniques, this study introduces a robust approach capable of integrating information from diverse medical image sources effectively. The utilization of convolutional networks to create weight maps enables the combination of pixel activity information from different input images, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of the fusion process. Moreover, the incorporation of image pyramids at multiple scales ensures that the fused images align well with human visual perception, thereby improving interpretability and clinical utility. One notable strength of the proposed method lies in its adaptive fusion mode adjustment based on local similarity, which enhances the fidelity of the fused images by intelligently adapting to variations in image characteristics across different regions.

The experimental results demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed approach, showcasing promising outcomes in terms of both visual quality and objective assessment metrics. This indicates its potential to significantly impact various clinical applications, ranging from disease diagnosis to treatment planning. Overall, the proposed method offers a comprehensive solution to the challenges associated with medical image fusion, paving the way for further advancements in this critical area of medical imaging research

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